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‘Ethics is transcendental’ (*Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus*, 6.421)

Abstract

My aim in this paper is to study and analyze Wittgenstein’s claim in the *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* that “Ethics is Transcendental” (TLP 6.421). Initially, I consider some interpretations that have been offered to account for the transcendental character of ethics in the *Tractatus* whilst, simultaneously, singling out the problems that stem from these interpretations and suggesting a need for an alternative account. Subsequently, I set out to offer said alternative account by resorting to Wittgenstein’s understanding of the transcendental character of logic –which encompasses taking Wittgenstein as endorsing a Kantian understanding of the notion ‘transcendental’. This leads to the claim that ethics is transcendental insofar as it is the condition of a certain ethical experience. Nevertheless, this account involves some inadequacies due to the incompatibilities between the *Tractatus* and the aforementioned Kantian understanding of the notion ‘transcendental’. Consequently, I identify the peculiarities of Wittgenstein’s understanding of the notion ‘transcendental’ and, on this basis, I set forth an adequate interpretation of his claim that ethics is transcendental. Specifically, I argue that, in the *Tractatus*, ethics is transcendental insofar as it is internal to or constitutive of a certain mystical view: valuing the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity.

Key words

Wittgenstein, *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus*, *Notebooks*, Transcendental, Ethics, Logic.

1. Introduction

Since the publication of the *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* (hereafter, *Tractatus*) Wittgenstein scholars have struggled to give an account of several of Wittgenstein's ideas, leading to a multitude of ongoing exegetical discussions.¹ This has been the case for the ethical propositions that occur at the end of the *Tractatus*, which constitute some of the most obscure and mystical passages of Wittgenstein's work. Throughout the present paper I want to try and shed some light on some of Wittgenstein's remarks and ideas on ethics. Specifically, I want to offer a coherent interpretation of Wittgenstein's claim that "Ethics is Transcendental" (*TLP* 6.421). To accomplish this task, I will divide my work into two main parts.

In section 2 I am going to consider some of the existing interpretations that have been offered in order to explain why Wittgenstein states that ethics is transcendental. First, I examine the possibility of conceiving Wittgenstein's claim in 6.421 as merely stating that ethics is transcendent. Second, I focus on the Transcendental Reading of the *Tractatus*, which is committed to the claim that Wittgenstein endorses the notion of a transcendental willing subject as the condition of ethics. Third, I study the possibility of resorting to Wittgenstein's *Notebooks* in order to claim that ethics, like logic, is a transcendental condition of the world. Fourth, I analyze the claim that ethics, like logic, is transcendental insofar as it is condition for the possibility of representation. Simultaneously, I single out the problems that stem from these interpretations and suggest

the need for an alternative account. In section 3 I set out to offer this alternative account of Wittgenstein's claim in 6.421 by resorting to Wittgenstein's understanding of the transcendentalism of logic and his characterization of ethics in the *Tractatus*.

2. A brief survey of some existing interpretations

The topic of transcendentalism in the *Tractatus* has been ever-present amongst Wittgenstein scholars. Generally, the focus on this topic has been centered on the possibility of viewing Wittgenstein as a transcendental idealist and, by extension, considering the possible ties between Wittgenstein's work and that of Kant. In this paper, however, I am not going to focus on this issue. Rather I want to turn my attention to a more puzzling remark made by Wittgenstein on the topic of transcendentalism: "Ethics is Transcendental" (*TLP* 6.421). A multitude of interpreters have tried to offer an adequate account of this proposition, but no consensus has been reached regarding how we must understand the transcendental character of ethics. In this section I want to briefly analyze some of the existing interpretations in order to point out a series of problems and inadequacies that suggest the need for an alternative account of Wittgenstein's claim in 6.421.

2.1 Ethics as merely transcendent

A common strategy consists in arguing that Wittgenstein, in 6.421, is uniquely claiming that ethics is transcendent (see e.g. Goodman 1982, 138, 142; Jacquette 1997, 318; Arnswald 2009, 8, 13-14; Mersch 2009, 28; Hughes 2009, 54; Oberdiek 2009, 179; Arrington 2017, 607). Namely, that ethics stands outside of the world (Hughes 2009, 55) –it is not traceable amongst the facts that constitute the world. The notion of transcendental, therefore, does not have a Kantian sense for Wittgenstein. "Ethics does

not consist in synthetic judgments known *a priori*: ethics for Wittgenstein lies ‘outside the world’ and therefore cannot be expressed in propositions” (Oberdiek 2009, 179), it is merely transcendent. Claiming that ethics is transcendent coincides with Wittgenstein’s general remarks about ethics in the *Tractatus*, where he states that ethical value must lie outside the world and no fact can inherently possess ethical value (TLP 6.4).

Replacing the notion ‘transcendental’ for the notion ‘transcendent’ also entails that ethics is accompanied by a myriad of other elements that conform the transcendentalia of the *Tractatus*. For instance, “pictorial, representational, logical-mathematical form, the metaphysical subject or philosophical ‘I’ (as distinct from the Cartesian psychological ego of ‘contemporary superficial psychology’), and propositional attitudes in psychological states” (Jacquette 1997, 318). Logic is also generally included amongst this transcendentalia, albeit some interpreters (see e.g. Hughes 2009, 54) offer a different (and more Kantian) definition of ‘transcendental’ when dealing with logic.

Nevertheless, this interpretation seems to be an inadequate account of Wittgenstein’s claim that ethics is transcendental. Whilst Wittgenstein did write ‘Ethics is transcendent’ in his *Notebooks*, “in the corresponding passage of the *Tractatus*, the word ‘transcendent’ has been replaced—and not incidentally, I believe—by ‘transcendental’ (MS 103,37 [NB 79]; TLP 6.421)” (Appelqvist 2012, 201). Wittgenstein seemed to be aware that there was a clear difference in meaning between the notions ‘transcendent’ and ‘transcendental’. Thus, his differentiated use of ‘transcendental’ in 6.421 suggests that we cannot limit the understanding of this proposition to merely transcendent. Any interpretation that wants to limit 6.421 to the mere claim that ethics is transcendent should offer a coherent explanation and justification of why we should substitute a notion that Wittgenstein explicitly uses (i.e. ‘transcendental’) for another notion that does not appear in the *Tractatus* and that has been discarded in 6.421 (i.e.

‘transcendent’). Moreover, it also raises the following question: why did Wittgenstein not use the notion ‘metaphysical’ to characterize ethics as merely transcendent? It is a notion that already appears in the *Tractatus* (e.g. TLP 5.632, 5.641) and its meaning seems to come close to that of ‘transcendent’: something which is neither an object or a fact, something that stands outside the world.

The claim that ethics is transcendent is perfectly legitimate (and can be justified in virtue of other propositions in the *Tractatus*, as shown above), but it is misguided to believe that it offers us a coherent account of Wittgenstein’s claim that ethics is transcendental. One may endorse the detailed account of the transcendence of ethics in the *Notebooks* and the *Tractatus* offered by Jacquette (1997). Nonetheless, it does not get us any closer to comprehending Wittgenstein’s remark in 6.421, where “ethics is not described as *transcendent*, that is, as being beyond the realm of the real, but as *transcendental*, that is, as a part of what conditions our experience of the real” (Christensen 2011, 802). This seems to be the reason why some interpreters claim that ethics is transcendent, but also provide a detailed account for the transcendental character of ethics (see e.g. Kelly 1995; Christensen 2011; Kuusela 2018; Kertscher 2009).

2.2 The Transcendental Reading of the *Tractatus*

Hacker (1986), Stokhof (2002), Schroeder (2006), Morris (2008) and Churchill (2009) among others, endorse a widespread reading of the *Tractatus* that has been labeled the ‘Transcendental Reading of the *Tractatus*’ –or ‘Schopenhauerian Reading of the *Tractatus*’. This reading argues that “Wittgenstein, in the *Tractatus*, endorses the notion of a transcendental subject as the condition of genuine religiousness (ethics) and – depending on the reading– representation” (Tejedor 2013: 57) –which generally entails drawing a comparison between Wittgenstein and Schopenhauer.² Said transcendental

willing subject, which Wittgenstein initially introduces in the *Notebooks*, is found in the *Tractatus* under the label of ‘metaphysical subject’. “According to the Transcendental Reading, it is in this light that we should interpret Wittgenstein’s claim, in the *Tractatus*, that: Ethics is transcendental” (Tejedor 2013: 57).

However, there are sufficient reasons to discard this reading as a viable account of the transcendental character of ethics in the *Tractatus*. In what follows I am going to reinstate some of the main objections that can be interposed against the Transcendental Reading (for more on this issue see Tejedor 2013; 2015; Fairhurst 2019). First, the employment of the *Notebooks* made by the Transcendental Reading seems to lead to a distortion of the contents of the *Tractatus* (Tejedor 2013: 56). For instance, there are a series of ethical remarks in the *Notebooks* that are not retained in the *Tractatus*. The Transcendental Reading opts to retain some of these entries (e.g. those concerning the willing subject), whilst discarding others without offering a detailed explanation and justification of this selection.

Second, it is unclear that the Transcendental Reading offers a correct interpretation of the *Notebooks*, since Wittgenstein does not seem to conceive the willing subject of the *Notebooks* as a transcendental condition of ethics. On the one hand, the Transcendental Reading resorts to the entry 5.8.16 to sustain its characterization of a transcendental willing subject, however this entry offers insufficient evidence for said characterization (see Fairhurst 2019: 83-84; Tejedor 2013, 57-62; 2015, 141-145). On the other hand, Wittgenstein explicitly states that ethics is transcendental (NB 30.7.16), and not the willing subject. This is due to the fact that if the willing subject were transcendental we could encounter circularity. Wittgenstein states: “if the will did not exist, neither would there be that center of the world, which we call the I, and which is the bearer of ethics” (NB 2015: 5.8.16). The will is conceived as the subject of ethical

attributes (TLP 6.423) and a condition for the existence of the I –the subject that possesses will in an ethical sense– (NB 2015: 2.8.16, 5.8.16, 4.11.16). Consequently, it is unclear how it could be argued that the willing subject, whose existence is dependent upon the will (the subject of ethical attributes), can be simultaneously a transcendental condition of ethics without encompassing some sort of contradiction or circularity. The subject’s existence would be dependent upon the subject of ethical attributes (i.e. the will), whilst simultaneously being the transcendental condition of these ethical attributes.

Finally, Wittgenstein in the *Tractatus* neither explicitly nor implicitly recognizes the existence of a transcendental willing subject under the label of ‘metaphysical subject’ (Tejedor, 57-62; 2015, 141-145; Fairhurst 2019, 92-93). The notion of transcendental is only used in relation to logic (TLP 6.13) and ethics (TLP 6.421), but there is no suggestion that this notion should be extended to the metaphysical subject. It follows from the above that the Transcendental Reading is an inadequate interpretation of Wittgenstein’s claim, in 6.421, that ethics is transcendental.

2.3. “Ethics must be a condition of the world” (NB 24.7.16).

An alternative strategy consists in focusing on Wittgenstein’s remarks in the *Notebooks* in order to offer an interpretation of 6.421 (see e.g. Christensen 2011, 802; Fairhurst 2019, 93-94). Specifically, it entails turning to the entry 24.7.16 of the *Notebooks* where Wittgenstein offers a precursor to the proposition 6.421 of the *Tractatus*: “Ethics does not treat of the world. Ethics must be a condition of the world, like logic. Ethics and aesthetics are one. [See 6.421.]” (NB 24.7.16). Thus, Wittgenstein provides us with a simple strategy to account for the transcendental character of ethics in the *Tractatus*. Despite the fact that ethics stands outside of the world, it is a condition for the existence of the world –just like logic (Fairhurst 2019, 93). Without ethics or logic our world would not exist. That ethics

is a condition of the world is shown, not in nonsensical utterances, but in our ability to represent the world in meaningful propositions (Christensen 2011, 802).³

Notwithstanding, whilst resorting to logic to account for the transcendental of ethics may prove to be a helpful strategy (as I will argue in section 3), this account is inadequate for two reasons. First, it illegitimately employs Wittgenstein's *Notebooks* in order to offer an interpretation of the *Tractatus*, thus distorting the contents of the *Tractatus* –a problem that has already been interposed against the Transcendental Reading in section 2.2. Wittgenstein abandons the formulation of 24.7.16 in the *Tractatus*, hence an explanation is required in order to justify why said formulation in the *Notebooks* is still a legitimate interpretation of 6.421 –despite no longer being present in the *Tractatus*. Nevertheless, until said explanation is provided, 24.7.16 should be seen as an “erratic diary entry from the time of the production of the *Tractatus* records” (Mersch 2009, 26) –just as many other entries of Wittgenstein's *Notebooks*.

Second, and emphasizing the previous problem, it is an inadequate interpretation of the transcendental character of ethics and logic. For instance, let us consider the case of logic in the *Tractatus*. Logic is of the utmost importance for Wittgenstein in the *Tractatus*: it plays a crucial role in our representation of reality. Any picture or representation of the world entails picturing “a situation in logical space, the existence and non-existence of state of affairs” (TLP 2.11). Consequently, all pictures (i.e. thoughts and propositions) must share a logical form with reality. We cannot picture any fact or state of affairs outside of logical space, since it would entail the possibility of picturing outside the limits of the world, outside of logic –a possibility that Wittgenstein denies (TLP 4.12). In consequence, whilst logic does precede any experience of the world (TLP 5.552), it is not a condition for the existence of the world –as the interpretation outlined above suggests. Rather it is a basic condition for our experience of reality: logic is a

precondition of our picturing of reality. Our thoughts and propositions, which constitute our experience of the world, must have a specific logical form to represent the world.⁴

Moreover, I believe the inadequacy of understanding the notion ‘transcendental’ as signifying ‘condition of the existence of the word’ is accentuated if we attempt to apply it to our interpretation of 6.421. How could ethics be a condition for the existence of the world? What necessary precondition does it provide? There seems to be no reason in the *Tractatus* to motivate or justify this interpretation: no proposition regarding ethics in the *Tractatus* deals with, or hints to, this possibility.

2.4. Ethics as a transcendental condition of representation

The characterization of logic leads us to a different way of interpreting the transcendental character of ethics. Given that logic is transcendental insofar as it is a condition of all our pictures (i.e. our representation of the world), it is reasonable to conclude that ethics is also transcendental in the same sense –since it is stated that both logic and ethics are transcendental (TLP 6.13, 6.421). This interpretation seems to be endorsed by Dain (2018, 20-21), who argues that in order to interpret Wittgenstein’s claim in 6.421 it is helpful to begin to understand the transcendental character of logic before returning to the case of ethics. Logic, like ethics, does not have a particular subject matter insofar as it does not consist of a set of substantive truths. This does not entail the elimination of logic, instead logic is the form of all thought. “Logic is, therefore, for Wittgenstein, a condition of all thought. There is no getting outside it” (Dain 2018, 21). How can this be extended to ethics? Dain suggests that one possibility is to follow Diamond (2000) and Christensen (2011), who claim that the point of calling ethics transcendental is that any thought may be, potentially, an ethical thought. However, Dain (2018, 22) claims that this view, whilst attractive, is problematic. First, under this view ethics is not transcendental.

Ethics would not be a condition of all thought, just some part of it –albeit there is no restriction on which part. But being the condition of some thoughts would entail that ethics, conversely to logic, would not be genuinely transcendental. Second, if not all thoughts are ethical, ethics would have a subject matter that could be determined via those thoughts that are ethical.

Against this view Dain offers the following interpretation:

Wittgenstein's view is, I think, that in delimiting thought and the expression of thoughts (from the inside), you thereby delimit the ethical (again *from* the inside): there is no further division among thoughts to be made, whether on the basis of their subject matter or not, and therefore there is no external perspective on ethics. (Dain 2018, 23)

Thus, ethics is transcendental in exactly the same sense in which logic is: ethics is a condition of all thought, every thought is an ethical thought (Dain 2018, 23). There is no getting outside of ethics. Hence, a viable interpretation has been offered for the transcendental character of ethics which resorts to its parallelism with logic.

Whilst I generally agree with the characterization of the transcendental character of logic offered by Dain, I think his claim that such a characterization can be directly extrapolated and applied to ethics is questionable. Wittgenstein's propositions suggest a strong connection between logic and our representation of the world in pictures. Throughout the *Tractatus* he insists on the crucial role that logic plays in picturing: pictures must be logical pictures (TLP 2.181, 2.182), they must share a logical form with reality (TLP 2.2, 4.12), they must represent possible states of affairs in logical space (TLP 2.202), and so on. Nevertheless, it seems that the *Tractatus* does not provide us with similar propositions for the case of ethics. Consequently, we are missing evidence in order to substantiate Dain's claim that the transcendental character of logic can be extrapolated and

extended to ethics directly. In the *Tractatus* the following is stated about the connection between ethics and pictures:

6.4 All propositions are of equal value.

6.41 The sense of the world must lie outside the world. In the world everything is as it is, and everything happens as it does happen: in it no value exists —and if it did exist, it would have no value.

If there is any value that does have value, it must lie outside the whole sphere of what happens and is the case. For all that happens and is the case is accidental.

What makes it non-accidental cannot lie within the world, since if it did it would itself be accidental.

It must lie outside the world.

6.42 So too it is impossible for there to be propositions of ethics. Propositions can express nothing that is higher.

6.421 It is clear that ethics cannot be put into words.

Ethics is transcendental.

(Ethics and aesthetics are one and the same.)

Wittgenstein, despite speaking about both ethics and pictures (propositions in this specific case), offers quite a negative view of their connection: it is simply impossible for there to be ethical propositions. Ethics simply cannot be put into words. This seems to dissipate the possibility of extending our understanding of the transcendental of logic to ethics. One might contend, nevertheless, that this initial characterization of the connection between ethics and pictures does not affect Dain's claim that the transcendental of logic can be extrapolated and extended to ethics directly, since Wittgenstein offers a similar characterization of logic: the propositions of logic say nothing (TLP 6.11).

Nonetheless, there seems to be a crucial difference: Wittgenstein appears to

introduce a complete excision between ethics and pictures (see e.g. TLP 6.42, 6.421, 6.423 and “A Lecture on Ethics”) that is not present when he speaks about logic and pictures. Logic and ethics share the impossibility of senseful propositions, but only logic is contained in all senseful uses of pictures –Wittgenstein offers no parallel statement for ethics in the *Tractatus*. Dain may object, however, that Wittgenstein does offer such evidence when he states that ethics is transcendental –hence all pictures are ethical pictures in some way or form.

Notwithstanding, I believe there are further issues with Dain’s proposal. First, Dain does not really explain how any particular mundane thought could have an ethical dimension. For instance, how does a proposition of specific area of physics have an ethical dimension? Dain (2018, 23) argues, however, that this is not problematic because Wittgenstein’s crucial thought is that ethics is present in all pictures insofar as ethics is a condition of all pictures –just as is logic. But this leads to a second and more serious issue. It is easy to see how one might conclude from the *Tractatus* that logic is a precondition of all pictures and, in consequence, that all pictures must be logical –thus accounting for the transcendental character of logic. But how is this account of transcendental extrapolated and applied to ethics?

Let us concede that all pictures are ethical. In order to apply the understanding of the transcendental character of logic to ethics, ethics must also be a precondition of all pictures. Whilst I believe arguments could be given in order to state that all pictures are ethical in some way or form, there seems to be no evidence for the claim that ethics is a precondition of all pictures. Logic is providing a logical form that is essential for any representation of the world. Hence why pictures must necessarily have a logical form, and it is in this sense that we can claim that all pictures are said to logical pictures. But what indispensable precondition of representation does ethics provide? What is the

necessary component of our pictures that is supplied by ethics? What is it that makes all pictures ethical pictures? Wittgenstein offers no such explanation in the *Tractatus* because there is simply no explanation to give. Ethics is not an essential condition for the possibility of representing or picturing the world. For Wittgenstein the sense/meaning of pictures is dependent upon two different elements: (i) they must be logical pictures (i.e. they must have a logical form that they share with reality) and (ii) they must represent the existence and non-existence of states of affairs. We do not find a third element that has to do with ethics. Thus, the challenge for Dain is not only explaining how all thoughts have an ethical dimension –as he himself recognizes (see Dain 2018, 23)–, but also explaining how ethics can constitute a precondition of representation, a transcendental precondition of all pictures.

In consequence, and in agreement with Appelqvist (2012, 201), we must conclude that, whilst there are good grounds to interpret the transcendental character of ethics in terms of preconditions, there are no good grounds to interpret it in terms of preconditions of representation. That is, ethics can be transcendental but it cannot be transcendental in exactly the same sense as logic.

3. “Ethics is transcendental” (TLP 6.421)

Up until this point I have considered a wide variety of existing interpretations of Wittgenstein’s claim that ethics is transcendental. Nevertheless, all these interpretations have been dismissed due to certain inadequacies that stem from their account of the transcendental character of ethics, thus suggesting the need for an alternative interpretation. Throughout the remainder of this paper I am going to set forth an alternative interpretation that attempts to avoid the issues outlined above whilst providing a coherent account of Wittgenstein’s claim in 6.421 of the *Tractatus*. I believe that the

most promising starting point has been hinted at in several of the accounts considered previously (see e.g. section 2.3 or 2.4): an adequate understanding of the transcendental of logic may prove useful and resourceful when dealing with the transcendental character of ethics. Let us then briefly reconsider the transcendental of logic.

3.1. “Logic is transcendental” (TLP 6.13)

Logic plays a crucial role in the *Tractatus*, as all pictures must necessarily share a logical form with reality. We cannot picture any fact or state of affairs outside of logical space, since it would entail the possibility of picturing outside the limits of the world, outside of logic –a possibility that Wittgenstein explicitly denies (TLP 4.12). Hence, for Wittgenstein there is no such thing as an illogical proposition or an illogical thought. If we combine this understanding of the role of logic in our picturing and representation of the world with the characterization of logic as “*prior to every experience*” (TLP 5.552), we obtain quite a straightforward (and Kantian) interpretation of Wittgenstein claim that “Logic is Transcendental” (TLP 6.13). Logic is a necessary precondition for our pictures, i.e. our thoughts and propositions (Kuusela 2018, 44). Our pictures (which constitute our experience of the world) must be logical pictures in order to represent the world –they must have a specific logical form that they share with the world. Logic, consequently, is transcendental insofar as it is a condition of the possibility of picturing the world. “Logical investigation is not concerned with anything in the world, but rather with the constitution of the world as an object of thought” (Kuusela 2018: 47).⁵

The notion ‘transcendental’ employed above can be understood by resorting to some parallels between Wittgenstein’s investigation in the *Tractatus* and Kant’s transcendental philosophy. For Kant transcendental philosophy

[...] is concerned with the necessary conditions of the possibility of cognitive experience (and in this sense with our mode of cognition of objects), its task being to draw limits to possible knowledge claims on the basis of a transcendental philosophical account of their *a priori* conditions of possibility. Similarly, Wittgenstein's investigation of the logical laws that govern thought is an investigation of the conditions of the possibility of thought. (Kuusela 2018, 44)

The parallel between Wittgenstein and Kant can shed some light on how to understand the notion 'transcendental' in the *Tractatus* in order to extrapolate it and subsequently apply it to ethics in order to offer an interpretation of 6.421.

Claiming that X is transcendental would come to mean something along the lines of:

X is an *a priori* necessary condition for the possibility of a certain (cognitive) experience.

For instance, in the case of logic we find that it is an *a priori* necessary condition for the possibility of picturing and representing the world (i.e. a cognitive experience). Hence, we have a general outline of the notion 'transcendental' in the *Tractatus* which avoids the issues pointed out in section 2.4, i.e. claiming that the notion 'transcendental' means exactly the same in relation to ethics and logic without the possibility of any substantial difference. The definition of 'transcendental' outlined offers the possibility of taking ethics and logic as being the *a priori* necessary conditions for the possibility of different cognitive experiences. Consequently, in what follows I am going to focus on establishing what kind of a cognitive experience requires ethics as an *a priori* necessary condition in order to extend these considerations regarding transcendentalism to ethics.

3.2. Preliminary approaches to the transcendental character of ethics

Within the literature we can find some interpretations that abide by the restrictions imposed on the notion ‘transcendental’, as described in section 3.1. For instance, Kelly (1995, 578) argues that both ethics and logic are not merely transcendent but also transcendental in the Kantian sense: they provide the conditions for the possibility of certain experiences. Logic, for instance, would constitute the “logical space which makes it possible for us to picture facts to ourselves in propositions” (Kelly 1995, 578). Meanwhile, Kelly (1995: 578) argues that ethics is transcendental insofar as it is the condition for the possibility of experiencing the world as a miracle created by God, thus constituting the ethical space that allows us to give meaning and value to our life. In summary, logic is a transcendental condition of logical space (which allows us to picture the world) and ethics is a transcendental condition of ethical space (which allows us to experience the world as a miracle created by God). Without logic there would be no facts and without ethics there are only ethically neutral contingent facts. Ethics provides a unifying perspective on life and the world that constitutes the ethical space that can introduce value and meaning in our life (Kelly 1995, 578).

Kelly, in addition, notes a further difference between logic and ethics. “In the case of logic there is, in effect, only one metaphysical subject constitutes a single common domain of facts” (Kelly 1995, 578). Notwithstanding, the situation differs when we turn to ethics. Wittgenstein states: “The world of the happy man is a different one from that of the unhappy man” (TLP 6.43). Consequently, and in strict contrast with logic, there is no longer a single ‘ethical space’ or a common domain of values (Kelly 1995, 578).

Kelly’s interpretation of the transcendental character of ethics, however, possesses some inaccuracies. The most significant one concerns how Kelly understands ethical space as involving an experience tied to viewing the world as a miracle created by God.

Whilst Wittgenstein, in his *Notebooks*, does discuss issues surrounding God and the relation between God and Ethics, such remarks are non-existent in the *Tractatus*. Wittgenstein only mentions God in the following four propositions of the *Tractatus*:

- 3.031 It used to be said that God could create anything except what would be contrary to the laws of logic. The truth is that we could not say what an ‘illogical’ world would look like.
- 5.123 If a god creates a world in which certain propositions are true, then by that very act he also creates a world in which all the propositions that follow from them come true. And similarly he could not create a world in which the proposition ‘*p*’ was true without creating all its objects.
- 6.372 Thus people today stop at the laws of nature, treating them as something inviolable just as God and Fate were treated in past ages.
- 6.432 *How* things are in the world is a matter of complete indifference for what is higher. God does not reveal himself *in* the world.

None of these four propositions seem to support Kelly’s claim that ethics involves viewing the world as a miracle created by God. The three first propositions appear to take the belief in God as an ancient tradition and introduce the idea of God in order to make a point about an altogether different issue –in no instance is Wittgenstein actually positing, or arguing in favor of, the existence of God. The only dubious proposition is 6.432, which could loosely be taken as admitting the existence of God. Nonetheless, this is irrelevant for the issue at hand, since it offers no evidence in favor of nor suggests an interpretation as that offered by Kelly. Wittgenstein does not require viewing the world as a miracle created by God in order to be ethical.

The passages of the *Notebooks* that openly discuss the idea of God seem to have

been abandoned by Wittgenstein at some point between 1916 and the publication of the *Tractatus*. Further evidence and justification is required in order to substantiate the claim that God plays a role in Wittgenstein's ethics in the *Tractatus*. This, in turn, entails that Kelly's account of the transcendental of ethics is insufficient –demonstrating again the importance of a correct utilization of the *Notebooks* in the interpretation of the *Tractatus*.

Another alternative is offered by Kertscher (2009) who, in concordance with Kelly, argues that ethics is not only transcendent but also transcendental in a Kantian sense, i.e. a condition for the possibility of an experience. The particular way in which ethics is transcendental is that it is the “condition for the possibility of responsible action” (Kertscher 2009, 108). Thus, ethics is an *a priori* condition for the possibility of all responsible actions. Nevertheless, this view seems problematic for two different reasons.

On the one hand, Kertscher's account of the transcendental of ethics seems to contradict his claim that ethics is transcendent (i.e. that ethics stands outside the world). The transcendence of ethics encompasses that no fact can inherently possess ethical value (TLP 6.4, 6.41). Hence the mark of ethical goodness and ethical badness cannot be registered amongst the facts that compose the world (e.g. empirical actions or empirical willing)⁶. However, Kertscher appears to tie ethics to a fact in the world: actions. Consequently, the transcendental of ethics conflicts with the transcendence of ethics. Notwithstanding, Kertscher may be able to solve this problem since he is aware about the fact that ethics is excluded from empirical life (see e.g. Kertscher 2009, 102, 105). Nevertheless, Kertscher must provide a more detailed explanation regarding the idea of ‘responsible action’ (in his work the only mention that can be found is in the quote supplied above), since it seems to play an important role in his interpretation of Wittgenstein's ethics.

On the other hand, Kertscher encounters a more serious problem. He argues that

ethics is transcendental in a Kantian sense. But the claim that ‘ethics is a condition for the possibility of responsible action’ does not seem to abide by this Kantian sense. As shown above, Kant’s transcendental philosophy “is concerned with the necessary conditions of the possibility of cognitive experience (and in this sense with our mode of cognition of objects)” (Kuusela 2018, 44). Consequently, something is transcendental if it is a condition for the possibility of a certain cognitive experience, if it plays a certain role in the way in which our mind constitutes objects in order to experience them. Kertscher’s account does not seem to fit this definition of transcendental, since responsible actions do not constitute a certain cognitive experience or a way in which in which our mind constitutes objects to experience them. Ethics, in consequence, should not be understood as a condition for the possibility of responsible action.

These shortcomings suggest the need for an alternative interpretation that abides by the definition of the notion ‘transcendental’ given in 3.2 whilst avoiding the problems outlined with regards to the proposals of Kelly and Kertscher. Throughout the following section I am going to turn to Wittgenstein’s ethics in the *Tractatus* in order to determine what experience is transcendentially preconditioned by ethics.

3.3. The transcendental of ethics

For Wittgenstein, and contrary to many of other ethical and moral philosophers, ethics must be situated outside of the world. Whilst all the facts that compose the world are accidental, absolute value (i.e. ethical value) is non-accidental (TLP 6.41). Ethical value cannot be tied to the world because it would become accidental and cease to have any value. In consequence ethics, in the *Tractatus*, has nothing to do with what we ordinarily associate with ethics. For instance, ethics will not involve a series of ethical laws or precepts that we must abide by when we carry out empirical actions (TLP 6.422). We will

not a find an ethical theory in the *Tractatus* that classifies empirical actions and conducts into morally good and morally bad. But Wittgenstein still believes that ethics concerns what is good and bad (specifically what is absolutely good and absolutely bad, as Wittgenstein explains in “A Lecture on Ethics”) and involves the ideas of ethical reward and ethical punishment. So what can ethics be about then? How can we obtain ethical reward and avoid ethical punishment? What is absolutely good and absolutely bad? Wittgenstein seems to focus on two main topics in ethics, around which he introduces a variety of subsidiary ideas.

On the one hand, we have the ethical will introduced in 6.423. Wittgenstein’s ethical will should not be understood or confused with our ordinary understanding of the will as a phenomenon. The good and bad exercise of ethical will does not alter any fact in the world, such as our actions or conduct. Rather it alters the limits of the world, making the world wax and wane as a whole, making it either a happy world or an unhappy world (TLP 6.43). Being able to alter the limits of the world entails viewing the world *sub specie aeterni* (TLP 6.45), i.e. viewing the world as a limited whole from outside space and time –and not amongst space and time, which would correspond to our ordinary empirical view of the world. “To understand our position in the world we must view it *sub specie aeternitatis*—as a limited whole. That is to say, no part of the world is privileged or preferred to another. [...] One’s life is seen as if from beyond” (Hughes 2009, 57). However, what does this alteration of the limits of the world involve? And how can we discern good ethical will from bad ethical will? It is generally argued that good ethical willing encompasses a certain attitude of harmony with reality, whilst bad ethical willing involves being in confrontation with reality (see e.g. Cavalier 1980, 159-160, 165-166, 173-175, 187-195; Worthington 1981, 486-489; Edwards 1982, 26, 46-47, 57, 67-68; Diamond 2000, 153-155; Churchill 2009, 113-114, 121-123; Hughes 2009, 52, 56-58;

Appelqvist 2013, 47-49, 51, 53; Kuusela 2018, 45-51; Fairhurst 2019, 88-89). Nevertheless, and regardless of the specifics that are involved in providing an answer to these questions, what is of the utmost importance for the task at hand is figuring out what experience is involved in ethically willing. Good willing entails experiencing the world as something (absolutely) valuable from an ethical standpoint. Meanwhile bad willing entails not experiencing the world as something absolutely valuable. In consequence, ethical willing (both bad and good) encompasses a certain attitude towards the world: a certain way of valuing the world in an absolute sense.

On the other hand, we have the problem of the meaning of life –a central ethical issue that Wittgenstein mentions in his *Notebooks*, *Tractatus* and “A Lecture on Ethics”. The riddle of life is introduced in 6.4312 where Wittgenstein states that contingent facts or the possibility of living eternally will offer no solution to this riddle. “The solution of the riddle of life in space and time lies *outside* space and time” (TLP 6.4312). The meaning of life must lie outside of the world –coinciding with Wittgenstein’s general transcendent characterization of ethics. Without delving into the controversial specifics about Wittgenstein’s ethical proposal, giving meaning to one’s life (i.e. solving the riddle of life and living a meaningful life) is tied to living a good ethical life. This, in turn, is accomplished through the main ethical action mentioned in the *Tractatus*: ethical willing. Good ethical willing will lead to transforming the limits of the world and giving meaning to one’s life; meanwhile bad ethical willing will result in the opposite. In consequence, giving meaning to one’s life (or failing to do so) is tied to our attitude to the world: to the way in which we value the world in an absolute sense.

Given this brief outline of Wittgenstein’s ethics, in what way can it be said that ethics is transcendental? What ethical experience is involved in Wittgenstein’s *Tractatus*? A first option would be to state that ethics is transcendental insofar as it is the condition

for the possibility of ethical willing. Nevertheless, this seems problematic insofar as ethical willing is an ethical action (albeit not an empirical action) and not an experience. An alternative option might lead us to suggest that ethics is transcendental insofar as it is the condition for the possibility of giving meaning to our life. Whilst this alternative is far more promising than the one considered previously, it still seems to be inadequate. This is due to the fact that solving the riddle of life (and, consequently, giving meaning to one's life) rests on a more fundamental experience: seeing the world from a perspective that shows the valueless world as valuable (Appelqvist 2012, 202). Let us turn our attention then to this fundamental experience and analyze in what way it can help us interpret Wittgenstein's claim in 6.421.

Kuusela (2018, 44) argues that whilst logic is concerned with the world as an object of thought or representation, ethics focuses on the constitution of the world as something valuable. In consequence, whilst logic is concerned with necessary conditions of the possibility of representation, ethics "is concerned with the possibility of a particular mode of our experience of the world, i.e., the experience of the world, which in itself is valueless and meaningless, as valuable and meaningful" (Kuusela 2018, 47). Namely, ethics is transcendental insofar as it is a condition for the possibility of valuing the world in an absolute sense.

Hence Kuusela focuses on the fundamental experience of valuing the world in order to account for the transcendental of ethics. Meanwhile Appelqvist turns to a slightly different fundamental experience. "The Tractarian notion of transcendental should be seen as indicating a shift of attention from certain factual experiences^[1] to their necessary preconditions" (Appelqvist 2012, 203). For instance, logic is transcendental insofar as it is the necessary precondition of symbolic representation –which gives us the world of facts. In the case of ethics Appelqvist (2012, 202-203; 2013, 52-53, 55) focuses

on the mystical experience that Wittgenstein introduces in relation to ethics (and aesthetics). Appelqvist argues that ethics is transcendental insofar as it is a transcendental precondition of those experiences that Wittgenstein calls ‘mystical’. Specifically, ethics is a transcendental precondition of the possibility of feeling the world as a limited whole under the aspect of eternity (Appelqvist 2012, 202-203; 2013, 55) –i.e. that which is ‘mystical’ (TLP 6.45).

Both Kuusela and Appelqvist turn to different experiences (which abide with the restrictions imposed on the transcendental of ethics up until this point) in order to account for Wittgenstein’s claim that ethics is transcendental. It seems, therefore, that we are faced with a choice between these two alternatives: is ethics a condition for the possibility of valuing the world or is it a condition for the possibility of feeling the world as a limited whole under the aspect of eternity? I believe both accounts are adequate, as they take ethics as a precondition of a fundamental ethical experience, but insufficient. This is due to the fact that valuing the world in absolute sense and feeling the world as a limited whole under the aspect of eternity are not separable experiences. Valuing the world in absolute sense entails feeling the world as a limited whole under the aspect of eternity and *vice versa*. Hence Kuusela’s and Appelqvist’s proposals are insufficient, but complementary. Their combination gives us a complete account of the transcendental character of ethics: ethics is transcendental insofar as is the precondition for the possibility of valuing the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity (i.e. *sub specie aeterni*). Valuing the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity (i.e. *sub specie aeterni*) is the fundamental ethical experience that is necessary in order to have a good ethical will and solve the riddle of life –thus, allowing us to live a good ethical life. In consequence, it seems that we have arrived at a complete and adequate interpretation of the transcendental character of ethics that overcomes all the problems

and abides by all the restrictions outlined throughout this paper.

3.4. Two further considerations

However, I believe this interpretation of the transcendental character of ethics is in need of two important amendments, which concern the Kantian approach to transcendentalism that has been employed throughout section 3. On closer inspection Wittgenstein's work suggests a slightly different understanding of the notion 'transcendental'. First, and following Tejedor's (2015, 126-127) deflationary understanding of the transcendental character of logic, I believe it is important to introduce an initial amendment to the characterization offered up until this point:

When Wittgenstein writes that logic is transcendental, he is not suggesting that it is a condition of either representation or the world. Logic is no more a condition of representation or of the world than representation or the world could be a condition of each other. (Tejedor 2015, 126)

Wittgenstein's account of the transcendentalism of logic is not as straightforward as it appears on the surface. The issues stem from the idea of 'condition', which introduces the idea of a mechanistic and external relation between logic and representation. In claiming that logic is a condition of representation it is suggested that logic is (i) conceptually prior to representation and (ii) can be specified independently of representation, thus allowing logic to be given in advance and in absence of representation (Tejedor 2015, 126-127). Hence, claiming that logic is a condition of representation opens up a gap between logic and representation (between logical form and pictures), treating them as two entirely different and separable things.⁷ However, such a gap contradicts Wittgenstein's treatment of logic, representation and pictures in the *Tractatus*, where he

treats them all as closely intertwined. In consequence, “logic is transcendental for Wittgenstein in that it is *internal to or constitutive of the correlation of representation and the world* (Tejedor 2015, 127). Logic is not conceptually prior to representation nor can it be specified independently from representation, rather it is internal to and constitutive of representation. With this deflationary understanding of the transcendental of logic it is possible to maintain the idea that logic is necessary and indispensable for the representation of the world, whilst avoiding the unnecessary and problematic commitments that stem from understanding logic as a transcendental condition.

This characterization of the transcendental character of logic, in turn, affects how we understand the case of ethics. Ethics is not conceptually prior nor can it be specified independently from the valuation of the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity (i.e. *sub specie aeterni*). Rather ethics is *internal to or constitutive* of the valuation of the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity (i.e. *sub specie aeterni*).

The second amendment concerns the employment of the notion ‘experience’ when dealing with Wittgenstein’s ethics. The definition of ‘transcendental’ offered in 3.2 suggested that X is transcendental if it is the condition for the possibility of a certain cognitive experience. However, it seems inadequate to speak about an experience with regards to the ethics of the *Tractatus*.⁸ This is due to Wittgenstein’s characterization of ethics. As shown above, he establishes a strict distinction between facts and ethics: ethics is transcendent, namely it is situated outside space and time. Meanwhile, Wittgenstein seems to tie the notion of experience to an event within space and time, a certain fact (cf. TLP 5.552, 5.634, 6.1222, 6.363, 6.4311; Wittgenstein 1965, 10). It seems, therefore, that ethics and experience are incompatible notions. Moreover, Wittgenstein seems to

explicitly make this claim in “A Lecture on Ethics” (1965, 8-10), where he attempts to detail certain ethical experiences before discarding them. This is due to the fact that, since they are experiences “they are facts; they have taken place then and there, lasted a certain definite time and consequently are describable” (Wittgenstein 1965, 10). It is a paradox to state that an experience has absolute ethical value. So how could ethics be constitutive of or internal to a certain cognitive experience? To overcome this issue I believe it is necessary to slightly modify the definition of the notion ‘transcendental’ in relation to ethics. Ethics, rather than being constitutive or internal to a certain experience, is constitutive of or internal to a certain *view* of the world. A view of the world that is not *cognitive*, but *mystical*. This understanding of the notion ‘transcendental’ allows us to avoid any unwanted contradictions with Wittgenstein’s ethics.

The two amendments outlined provide us with a modified understanding of the transcendental character of ethics. Ethics is no longer transcendental in the Kantian sense (i.e. it is a condition for the possibility of a certain cognitive experience); rather it is transcendental insofar as it is internal to or constitutive of a certain mystical view. Applying this definition of ‘transcendental’ to the account offered in 3.3 results in interpreting Wittgenstein’s claim about the transcendental character of ethics in 6.421 as follows:

Ethics is transcendental insofar as it is internal to or constitutive of the valuation of the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity (i.e. *sub specie aeterni*).

To conclude I would like to briefly outline two further differences between the transcendental character of ethics and that of logic. First, logic is internal to or constitutive of a cognitive experience within space and time (i.e. representing), meanwhile ethics is internal to or constitutive of a mystical view outside space and time. Logic constitutes the

world as an object of representation, whilst ethics constitutes the world (as a limited whole) as an object of ethical evaluation. Second, Wittgenstein considers that is not possible to experience the world without being constrained by logic, there are no such as illogical thoughts (TLP 5.4731). “We could not say *what* an ‘illogical’ world would look like” (TLP 3.031). Nonetheless, and conversely to logic, it is possible to be unethical and not comply with what is required to be ethically good and live a good ethical life. Ethics is constitutive of a specific way of viewing the world as something valuable in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity. Nonetheless, it is possible to be unethical and view the world as something valueless.

Conclusion

This paper has dealt with the problem regarding how to interpret Wittgenstein’s claim that “Ethics is Transcendental” (TLP 6.421). On the one hand, I have analyzed a series of existing interpretations and singled out the problems that they encounter in order to show the need for an alternative understanding of the transcendental character of ethics. On the other hand, I have set out to offer said alternative interpretation. First, I analyzed in what way logic is transcendental in the *Tractatus* in order to offer a definition of the notion ‘transcendental’ and, subsequently, extrapolate it and apply it to ethics. Second, I considered two preliminary approaches, offered by Kelly and Kertscher, which abided by this definition. However, both interpretations were dismissed due to the problems they encountered. Third, I turned to Wittgenstein’s ethics in the *Tractatus* in order to search for the cognitive experience that is transcendently preconditioned by ethics. This leads to two possible alternatives: stating that ethics is the transcendental condition of the possibility of valuing the world in an absolute sense (as argued by Kuusela) or that it is the transcendental condition of the possibility of feeling the world as a limited whole

under the aspect of eternity (as argued by Appelqvist). I suggested that whilst both alternatives are insufficient, they are also complementary. Their combination gives us a complete account of the transcendental character of ethics: ethics is transcendental insofar as it is the precondition for the possibility of valuing the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity (i.e. *sub specie aeterni*). Finally, I introduced two amendments to this alternative interpretation in order to avoid any further inadequacies. On the one hand, and resorting to Tejedor, I outlined a deflationary understanding of transcendentalism where the idea of ‘condition’ pertaining to the Kantian definition of ‘transcendental’ is substituted by the idea of ‘being internal to or constitutive of’. On the other hand, I argued that ethics is not internal to or constitutive of a certain ethical experience, since for Wittgenstein it is paradoxical to state that there is such a thing as an ethical experience. In consequence, ethics is better understood as transcendental insofar as it is internal to or constitutive of a certain mystical view. The application of these two amendments resulted in interpreting Wittgenstein’s claim about the transcendental character of ethics in 6.421 thus: ethics is transcendental insofar as it is internal to or constitutive of the valuation of the world in an absolute sense under the aspect of eternity (i.e. *sub specie aeterni*).

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¹ I will use the abbreviation ‘TLP’ to cite the *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* and the abbreviation ‘NB’ to cite Wittgenstein’s *Notebooks*.

² For a more detailed characterization of this reading see Appelqvist (2013, 41), Tejedor (2013; 2015) and Fairhurst (2019).

³ Albeit Christensen does seem to distance herself from this position at times.

⁴ I will turn to this the transcendental character of logic in more detail section 3.

⁵ Implicit in this characterization of the transcendental character of logic lays an important lesson about the utilization of the *Notebooks* when interpreting the *Tractatus*. Resorting to the *Notebooks* generally leads to the claim that logic is a condition of the world –which is then extended to account for the transcendental character of ethics. However, as shown, logic is not a condition of the world. It is the condition for the possibility of representing and picturing the world. At most, it is “a condition of the possibility of the world as the object of thought” (Kuusela 2018, 47).

⁶ This problem is quite widespread amongst interpreters who take Wittgenstein’s ethics as having consequences in our empirical actions (see, e.g., Mulhall 2007, 232-233, 236, 243-245; Hughes 2009, 52; Oberdiek 2009, 177, 185, 190)

⁷ This account of the transcendental character of logic encompasses a problem that is reminiscent of one of the main issues that stems from associating Wittgenstein with metaphysical realism. Some interpreters (see e.g. Anscombe 1971; Hacker 1986; 1996; 2017) take Wittgenstein as advancing, in the ontological passages in the 1s and 2s of the *Tractatus*, a doctrine or a theory that characterizes reality independent of how we think about it or represent it in propositions (i.e. a language and thought independent reality). World and pictures are treated as two independent totalities that have a sizeable gap between them that we must breach – Hacker, for instance, resorts to the transcendental subject to accomplish this. One of the problems with this reading is that the gap between ‘world’ and ‘pictures’ is non-existent in the *Tractatus* (Ishiguro 1969; McGuinness 1981; McGinn 1999; Moyal-Sharrock 2007; Goldfarb 2011; MacNeil 2017). This problem is accentuated when we take into account that any explanation that attempts to breach the gap leads to cosmic exile or god’s eye understanding: “the search for a point from which we can view the relation between language (or thought) and the world independently of our own situation in the world” (Williams 2004: 1). Hence we would require a cosmic exile to account for the external relation between world and pictures. These problems seem to reappear when we take ‘transcendental’ as involving the idea of condition: we conceive pictures and logic separately, establishing a gap between both of them that must be breached with some sort of explanation. But this gap is non-existent in the *Tractatus*, thus an alternative explanation is required.

⁸ Kelly also employs the notion of experience when dealing with the transcendental character of ethics.